

Leveraging Intelligent Social Tutoring System to Address Social-Emotional Learning in Elementary Schools

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Abstract. Research has shown that students with strong social-emotional skills demonstrate greater motivation to learn, have more positive attitudes toward school, participate more actively in activities, and show better academic performance than students with social-emotional challenges. However, many students who stand to benefit from such programs currently do not receive the help they need due to logistical barriers that limit the scalability of traditional in-person social-emotional instruction. This research provides an evidence-based solution by implementing and studying a technology- and game-based program that incorporates an intelligent social tutoring system with effective teaching strategies of scaffolding, coaching and reinforcement, and practice with feedback, as well as effective social skill trainings. We conducted a multi-site cluster randomized experimental study to address the educational efficacy of the program on students' social-emotional competency. Results suggest that the program has a significant and positive impact on students' social-emotional skills. It benefits all students, including students with social-emotional challenges, demonstrating that the program is an appropriate resource for diverse learners.

Keywords: Intelligent Social Tutoring System, Social-emotional Learning, Technology-based Intervention, Randomized Controlled Trials, Efficacy

1 Introduction

Healthy social-emotional development is particularly important because it impacts the whole child. Students with good social-emotional skills have better academic performance and school behaviors [5,21], fewer behavioral problems [6], better relationships with peers and family [3], and fewer mental health issues [9,17]. Students who have difficulty navigating the social developmental shifts of school are more likely to experience academic underachievement, behavioral problems, and emotional difficulties [15]. Poor social skills place students at a heightened risk for bullying, teasing, and social isolation [18]. As students experience social failure, school becomes an aversive environment that may further evoke negative avoidant behaviors [8]. In fact, there is a direct correlation between being bullied at school and increased absenteeism, which in turn negatively impacts students' academic performance [11,12].

Despite the availability of proven social-emotional learning interventions, many students who stand to benefit from such programs fail to receive the help they need due to

logistical barriers of implementing traditional in-person, social-emotional learning programs [1,22]. Social-emotional learning programs in schools are typically delivered by school support staff (e.g., school counselors), and there is often inadequate funding to cover their time. Additional realities can often erode the sustainability of in-school social-emotional learning programs, such as: competing priorities, the unavailability or lack of time from overwhelmed staff, inadequate tools to support ongoing implementation, insufficient staff training in social-emotional learning instruction, and instructional drift [1,10]. Student engagement can also present an issue, with providers commonly reporting that motivating children to engage in traditional interventions is among their most difficult tasks [2]. Finally, there remains a stigma associated with receiving mental health or behavioral services, and an in-person intervention might dissuade some from seeking helpful treatment. These obstacles prevent many high-needs students from receiving effective, high-quality social-emotional learning instruction, posing a significant barrier to scaling effective social-emotional learning practices.

Technology-based interventions provide the opportunity to reduce common barriers to treatment and effectively deliver evidence-based social-emotional learning content to diverse learners [20]. Technology-based interventions reduce costs and offer flexibility in timing, maximizing the number of students who can benefit and the frequency of interaction [23]; provide standardized administration of content, greatly reducing potential fidelity concerns associated with inadequate training of providers and instructional drift [7]; and allow for stigma-free practice opportunities within a protected, safe virtual environment [23].

In our paper, we discuss a randomized controlled trial study that examines the effectiveness of an online interactive social-emotional learning program - *Adventures Aboard the S.S.GRIN* (henceforth *Adventures*) - in elementary schools. In particular, we will address the following research questions:

1. Is the *Adventures* program treatment more effective than the control for improving students' social-emotional skills?
2. Is the *Adventures* program treatment more effective than the control for improving students' social-emotional skills for students with social-emotional challenges and students with different ethnic backgrounds?

2 Adventures Aboard the S.S.GRIN

For technology-based interventions to be effective and result in observable student improvements in real-world settings, the instructional content must be built on a solid theoretical and research foundation. *Adventures*, an online interactive social-emotional learning program, is designed to translate the content and cognitive-behavioral strategies of an established, evidence-based social skill training program – Social Skills Group Intervention (S.S.GRIN) – into a game-based virtual world. Developed by 3C Institute, *Adventures* leverages a unique use of technology to address critical social-emotional skills. It uses a single-player format and intelligent social tutoring system to provide individualized feedback and a safe environment for practicing newly learned skills to regulate emotions, control impulses, build friendships, and respect self and

others. Intelligent social tutoring system transformed effective traditional in-person social-emotional learning into the digital *Adventures* version, making it the first available evidence-based social-emotional game for upper elementary students. The intelligent social tutoring game engine was specifically designed to actively engage children in social problem-solving tasks through adaptive interactive software technology. The overall design of *Adventures* represents a unique collaboration between experts in child psychology and computer science, incorporating effective training strategies derived from research in education, intelligent tutoring systems, and social skills interventions.

Adventures uses a social-justice-oriented approach to address educational equity. This effective and equitable approach builds on the same social skills driving the racial and social justice movement [16]. It emphasizes empathizing with and respecting others, navigating social conflicts effectively, and standing up for justice and fairness. *Adventures* features practical, research-based, and theoretically sound instructional episodes that teach and provide practice for essential social relationship building skills (Table 1). To maximize student engagement, the instructional episodes are set within an appealing story narrative: the player joins a ship crew and travels around a fictional island, interacting and problem-solving with a host of characteristics. To increase the ease of transferring social-emotional learning skills to real life, the game’s social problems and discourse simulate social situations, such as staying calm in emotionally charged situations, expressing emotions positively, and cooperating and compromising with peers. Lines of mystery and mini cliffhangers are woven throughout the story to maintain student engagement across episodes.

Table 1. Adventures Episode Topics

Episode	Instructional Topic
1	Respect (self-respect and respecting others)
2	Looking Towards the Future (consequences, role models, and action plans)
3	Taking Responsibility (responsibility and impulse control)
4	Communicating (verbal and nonverbal; productive and receptive)
5	Understanding the Situation (assumptions and perspective taking)
6	Building Friendships (friendship skills and social initiation)
7	Cooperating with Others (cooperation, compromise, and peer pressure)
8	Emotion Regulation (emotional self-awareness, regulation, and interference)
9	Review and integration across social skills

As students navigate *Adventures*, the software captures in-game behaviors, and these data are used to assess progress in real-time and individualize the game experience for students. Some in-game behaviors are dialog-driven menu choices (e.g., choosing the best verbal response from a set of choices), whereas others are more general game-based actions (e.g., choosing when to talk to another character, sequence of social actions). Other game-based behaviors, such as perseveration (i.e., repeating a particular response or behavior) and time off task, are also used to adapt what is presented to the student. The software tracks children’s interactions and calculates performance indices for each social problem-solving task and for overall achievement. At appropriate times, individualized feedback is provided in response to the student’s performance. All dialog

and other text are accompanied by audio voiceover to account for differences in reading ability and to convey important social information, such as emphasis and tone of voice. The program generates a detailed performance report via the Teacher Dashboard indicating whether the student is at the emerging, improving, or proficient level for corresponding social-emotional skills.

3 Methods

3.1 Research Design

The study utilized a multi-site cluster randomized design, which randomly assigned third-grade classrooms to one of two conditions—a treatment condition that used *Adventures*, or a control condition that used the school’s business-as-usual program(s). The study was conducted with two cohorts from 2019-20 and 2020-21, respectively, in 88 third-grade classrooms from 37 schools across four California public school districts. For each cohort, the number of classrooms per school ranged from one to four, including 13 schools with only one teacher. For schools with an even number of participating classrooms, we randomly assigned classrooms within schools to a treatment or control group. For schools with an odd number of participating classrooms, we paired schools based on four matching variables (percent of students who received free and reduced lunch, percent of English Learners, percent of Hispanic students, and percent of White students). We then randomly assigned teachers within each pair to the treatment or control group. Forty-four classrooms (793=students) were randomly assigned to treatment, and 44 classrooms (n=852 students) were randomly assigned to control.

3.2 Participants

Sixty-five percent of the participating schools are Title I schools. The average class sizes for treatment and control classrooms were 18 and 19, respectively. Analysis of the student demographic data indicated that about one-third of the students were Latinx, and about 50% qualified for free and reduced lunch. There were no statistically significant differences between the treatment and control groups regarding ethnicity, free and reduced lunch status, gender, and English Language Learner status (Table 2).

Table 2. Student Demographic Characteristics for the Study Sample by Condition

Demographic Characteristics	Treatment	Control	Total	<i>p</i>	Effect size
Hispanic	31.80%	30.76%	31.23%	0.719	0.03
Free and Reduced Lunch	46.73%	51.31%	49.23%	0.183	-0.11
Male	49.06%	49.38%	49.24%	0.912	-0.01
English Language Learner	11.90%	10.48%	11.12%	0.428	0.09

Note. Effect size was computed based on Cox index. The *p*-value was obtained based on Fisher’s exact test.

3.3 Measures

Screening Measure: Devereux Student Strengths Assessment-Mini (DESSA-Mini). The DESSA-Mini is an eight-item behavior rating scale used to screen for social-emotional competencies of K-8 students. The measure is nationally standardized and has excellent psychometric properties, with an internal reliability of .92, a test-retest reliability of .94, and an inter-rater reliability of .77 [14]. The validity study indicates that the DESSA-Mini can be used with confidence as a screener for social-emotional competence. Students whose Social-Emotional Total score is 40 or below are identified as at risk for developing social-emotional problems.

SELweb. This is a performance-based assessment of social-emotional skills [13] that examines students' skills across 12 scenarios. It was designed to assess emotion recognition and social perspective-taking, social problem-solving, and delay of gratification and frustration tolerance. The validity study focusing on construct and criterion validity indicated SELweb possesses desired psychometric properties. The Cronbach's alpha is .83, and the test-retest reliability is .59.

Zoo U. Created by the developer of *Adventures*, *Zoo U* is a game platform that assesses social-emotional skills in children pertaining to communication, cooperation, empathy, emotion regulation, impulse control, and social initiation. *Zoo U* demonstrated high internal consistency (McDonald omega coefficient = .81) and criterion validity in predicting externalizing and internalizing behavioral problems [4].

4 Data Analysis

To address whether *Adventures* is more effective than the control for improving students' social-emotional skills (RQ 1), we used a series of two-level hierarchical linear models with a random intercept and fixed treatment effect, where the dependent variable in each model is a separate social-emotional learning outcome. In each model, the effect of treatment on an outcome measure is estimated at the classroom level, controlling for student pretest scores and background information (gender and ethnicity). The blocks used for the random assignment were treated as the fixed effect in the models. The model takes the following form:

Level-1: Student Level

$$Y_{ij} = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}(\text{pre}Y_{ij}) + \sum \beta_{2.mj}X_{mij} + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

Level-2: Cluster (Teacher) Level

$$\beta_{0j} = \gamma_{00} + \gamma_{01}(T_j) + \sum \gamma_{02,p}\text{Block}_{pj} + \mu_{0j}$$

$$\beta_{1j} = \gamma_{10}$$

$$\beta_{2.mj} = \gamma_{2.m0}$$

Where, Y_{ij} is the outcome for the i^{th} student in the j^{th} class; β_{0j} is the intercept for class j ; β_{1j} is the point estimate of pretest in class j ; $\text{pre}Y_{ij}$ is a pretest measure for the i^{th} student in the j^{th} class; $\beta_{2.mj}$ is the point estimate associated with m student covariates

in class j ; X_{mij} is the m^{th} of M additional covariates for student i in class j ; ε_{ij} is an error term for student i in class j ; γ_{00} is the mean intercept; γ_{01} captures the treatment effect; T_j is a dichotomous variable indicating whether class j was assigned to treatment or control condition; γ_{10} is the mean effect of student pretest; $\gamma_{2.m0}$ is the mean effect of additional student covariate X_m ; Block_{pj} indicates whether the class j was assigned to the treatment or control condition within the block p (where p is the number of blocks minus 1); $\gamma_{02.p}$ reflects the fixed effect of Block p ; and μ_{0j} is the random intercept term at level 2. To determine whether the *Adventures*' treatment is more effective than the control for improving students' social-emotional skills when treating students with prior social-emotional challenges (research question 2), an interaction term, treatment by students' prior social-emotional challenges status measured by DESSA-Mini was added to the model. A similar model was used by adding an interaction term, treatment by students' ethnicity, to determine whether the *Adventures*' treatment effects varied by ethnic groups.

5 Results

Table 3 summarizes the treatment impact between the treatment and control groups (indicated in the "Diff" column), along with the adjusted means and unadjusted standard deviations for each outcome measure. The treatment group scored significantly higher than their counterpart on both outcome measures, with an effect size of .6 for *Zoo U* and .41 for SELweb. The estimated average treatment effect based on *Zoo U* is .53 ($p < .001$) and .41 for SELweb ($p < .001$).

Table 3. The Effect of Adventures on Student Social-Emotional Skills

	Adjusted mean		Diff	SE	p-value	Hedges' g	Tx (n)	Tx (SD)	Cx (n)	Cx (SD)
	Tx	Cx								
<i>Zoo U</i>	0.29	-0.24	0.53	0.044	<.001	0.60	588	0.808	725	0.917
SEL-web	0.51	0.10	0.41	0.039	<.001	0.41	578	1.001	716	1.016

Adventures seemed to benefit all students in the treatment group, regardless of their social-emotional challenge status measured at the baseline, as indicated in Table 4. Based on *Zoo U* and SELweb, students identified as having social-emotional challenges in the treatment group gained more than their counterparts in the control group (difference=.59 and .45, respectively, significant at the .05 level). The gains were also true for students not identified as having social-emotional challenges (difference=.49 and .38, respectively, significant at the .05 level). The treatment by challenge status interaction (i.e., the difference of difference indicated by the contrast column) is .10 and .065, respectively, and both are not statistically significant at the .05 level. Given that not many students were identified as having social-emotional challenges in either the treatment or control group, the study may not have sufficient statistical power to detect such treatment by challenge interaction effect.

Table 4. The Effect of *Adventures* on Student Social-Emotional Skills, by Social-Emotional Challenge Status Measured by DESSA-Mini

	Tx adjusted mean (n)	Cx adjusted mean (n)	Mean Diff	Contrast	SE	p-value	Hedges' g
<i>Zoo U</i>							
DESSA	0.13 (91)	-0.46 (146)	0.59		0.124	<.001***	0.68
Non-DESSA	0.30 (497)	-0.18 (579)	0.49		0.056	<.001***	0.56
				0.10	0.131	0.433	0.12
SELweb							
DESSA	0.51 (90)	0.06 (141)	0.45		0.116	0.001**	0.44
Non-DESSA	0.50 (488)	0.12 (575)	0.38		0.056	<.001***	0.38
				0.07	0.127	0.606	0.06

Note. "DESSA" refers to those students with social-emotional challenges; "non-DESSA" refers to those students without social-emotional challenges.

** : significant at .01 level; ***: significant at .001 level

Similarly, *Adventures* appeared to benefit all students in the treatment group more than the control group, regardless of their ethnicity (Table 5). In particular, Hispanic students seemed to gain even more than non-Hispanic students. The interaction effect (as indicated by the contrast column) is 0.22 for *Zoo U* and is significant at .05 level, with an effect size of 0.26. The contrast for SELweb is 0.15 (not significant at .05 level) with an effect size of 0.15.

Table 5. The Effect of *Adventures* on Student Social-Emotional Skills, by Ethnicity (Hispanic vs. non-Hispanic)

	Tx adjusted mean (n)	Cx adjusted mean (n)	Mean Diff	Contrast	SE	p-value	Hedges' g
<i>Zoo U</i>							
Hispanic	0.42 (187)	-0.27 (223)	0.68		0.075	<.001***	0.78
Non-Hispanic	0.23 (401)	-0.23 (502)	0.46		0.055	<.001***	0.53
				0.22	0.098	0.022*	0.26
SELweb							
Hispanic	0.52 (182)	0.01 (220)	0.51		0.072	<.001***	0.51
Non-Hispanic	0.50 (396)	0.14 (496)	0.36		0.052	<.001***	0.36
				0.15	0.096	0.116	0.15

6 Conclusions and Future Work

The study emphasized on the effectiveness of using intelligent social tutoring system - an innovative technology embedded in a digital game format called the *Adventures Aboard the S.S. GRIN* - to improve the social-emotional outcomes of third grade students from high needs schools. The results from the study indicated that *Adventures* was positively and significantly associated with gains in students' social-emotional skills related to communication, cooperation, empathy, emotion regulation, impulse control, and social initiation (as measured by *Zoo U* measures) as well as emotion recognition, social perspective-taking, social problem-solving, delay of gratification, and frustration tolerance (as measured by SELweb). Similarly, a subgroup analysis of students with different social-emotional skills and ethnicity groups revealed that *Adventures* benefitted all students in the treatment condition.

Adventures provides an example of leveraging intelligent social tutoring system and effective design strategies to empower practical, theoretically sound social-emotional programs and create accessible learning experiences. Many of the barriers associated with scaling in education involve interventions or instructional approaches that require a significant amount of time, resources, human capital, and systems-level changes. This often leads to a very slow rollout and/or only incremental change in improving student outcomes. Because *Adventures* is engaging and easy to implement without intensive professional development, it does not require a major change in education practice, making it uniquely positioned to be accessible to larger population.

The implementation of *Adventures* in school environments contributes to a growing effort to support all students' social-emotional learning, especially those experiencing social-emotional challenges who stand to benefit the most from such interventions. Developers of intelligent social tutoring systems such as *Adventures* can further leverage play and narrative episodes in their designs to create interactives that encourage meaningful, active child-centered learning, building socio-technical structures in the process that engage users and allow for the continual growth of individuals within the communities and cultures in which they are nested. Researchers can further examine in-episode behavior, including the degree to which students pay attention while solving in-episode problems (e.g., listening to audio narrative before making a choice) and the likelihood that they are trying to game the system (e.g., always choosing the worst option or always choosing the first menu option). These studies help define not only whether students solve the social problems presented to them, but how they solve them, which is essential for personalized learning and scaffolding purposes.

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